

Policies Contribution and Integrated Quality Management to Improve the Quality of Services in Primary and Secondary Education in the Banten of Province 21 St Centuruy The Era of the Revolutionary 4.0

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ABSTRACT: the success of an organization is largely determined by the management model that is applied, sedangkan keberhasilan manajemen ditentukan oleh pemimpinnya especially in primary and secondary education which has a central and very strategic role for the continuation of the next higher education. this strategic role will be more effective if educational institutions can implement integrated quality management education services in the 21st century revolutionary 4.0, This management model is considered appropriate, because this management focuses on customer satisfaction, both internal customers and external customers.

on this basis in this study, researchers used a quantitative descriptive research approach with descriptive statistics, while the focus of the problem was ; “policy contribution and integrated quality management in improving the quality of basic and secondary education services in Banten province in the 21st century revolutionary 4.0 ”, to get data the researcher acts as a human instrument, and is assisted with data collection guidelines such as interview guidelines, observation and questionnaire, addressed to the research data source as many as ninety heads and ninety teachers.

From the results of the research and discussion, it can be stated that the contribution of integrated policies and quality management in improving the quality of education services Primary and secondary education in the Banten province of the 21st century industrial revolution 4.0 contributed well to an average of 0.232 for elementary school, 0.246 for junior high school and 0.214 for upper secondary school.

on this basis, it is time for the establishment of primary and secondary education to be unable to implement a service management model, because of this service management model, expected to improve the quality of services in primary and secondary education effectively, continuously and continuously .

KEYWORDS: Integrated Service Quality Management

INTRODUCTION

Education is one form of industry, service industry, while education services provided are, 1) academic services, 2) financial administration services, 3) student administration services, 4) research services, 5) community services. Service is a complex phenomenon, because services have many different understandings with understanding such as: service from someone to someone else (Farida Jasfar, 2005:2). The service was as a process of produkmelibatkan in the input (input) and menstranformasikannya into the output (output/outcome), (Muhtosim Arief, 2005:11). Difinition this is very relevant to the process of education services, because in the activities of the educational process is always associated with various approaches, one approach is to use a system that is is an activity that process the input (input) for. .made the output/results (output) with the menghasilkan impact (outcome) that has a value of competitive and comparative superior, because its products are human. Given the nature of the quality of education is learning, quality, while the nature of the quality of learning is the quality of the results of the study, and the nature of the quality of learning outcomes is the quality of human resources, thus the beginning and end of the beginning and the quality of education perceived quality shutter on the achievement of results ..readinessWhile the indicators against which became the primary quality is; (1) prior to the formation of the personality of the students on a regular basis and grow into a virtuous man and a sublime calm and, (2) the grant of the basic capabilities of the intelektual ... (read write

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andcounting). (H.R. Tilaar, 2002:176). Therefore, the primary school has a central role and strategic significance in the process of human *pencerdasan*, in which case the failure of the education at primary school level, will can lead to the failure of education at a higher level.

Next. On the basis of this is on this occasion the author focus kegitan research on elementary school, First School Menengan and secondary school with the focus of the research are: "The contribution of the policy and management of Pendidikan Terpadu in improving the quality of Education of the 21st century the Era of the revolution ..4.0 industry. in Banten Province.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The essence of the integrated services quality management is the gratification of the customer, through the involvement of all elements in all processes (integrated), whereas the essence of the Service/service (services) is the fulfillment of customer expectations. .In this oration I focuses on the study of service/education services, as for the education service has a central role and very strategic as well as the non discrimination in the liberation of mankind from ignorance is a service learning activity, in order for the service This learning activity can. .take place with good power needed support from other services such as; 1 academic administration services (JA), 2) General Administration Services (JAU), 3) financial administration services (JAK), and 4) extracurricular Services (JEK), 5) services library, 6) laboratory services, as well as specifically for. .higher education or universities including, 7) Research (JP) and 8). community services (JPM), (Farida Jafar, 2005:2). The services of the educational process, including services that are intricate and complex, is said to be complex because it served were human, while said to be complicated, since it is a series of process system, which processes "input into results", while the It has a central role and strategic ..in service learning is the teacher and/or lecturer, who simultaneously acts as customer services. In order for this educational process service activity to succeed well, it is better that the implementation of integrated service quality management should pay attention to three strategic service triangle namely; 1) service strategy namely; prioritizing the best service, 2) resource strategy .humans namely; availability of competent and professional human resources, 3) system strategy; that is; a service system that involves everyone, and all facilities effectively. .(Sudadio, 2015: 7).The success of service management will be more effective if there is concrete support, namely; 1) the commitment of the leadership, 2) the existence of qualified educators and staff, both quantitatively and qualitatively, 3) the existence of a quality vision, 4) continuous improvement and .continuous, 5) good communication between service providers and customers, and 6) appreciation and recognition of service success, Nasution, 2014 (sudadio, 2015: 3).

QUALITY OF SERVICES

Service quality is a measure of the level of service provided, namely; how well the quality of services provided is able to meet or meet customer expectations, Lewis and Booms, 1983, (Sudadio: 2015: 15). .While the nature of the quality of education is; quality of learning, the nature of the quality of learning is the quality of learning outcomes, and the nature of the quality of learning outcomes is the quality of human resources, and the nature of quality human resources is competent and professional. .Quality, is the need of everyone, but demands for quality are sometimes different; there are those who demand absolute quality, there are those who demand ordinary quality, and there are also those who want quality relatively or according to the customer's interest, all of these choices are very much determined by perception ..and the needs of the customers themselves, when ya feel hope and kebutuhanya already fulfilled, and feel satisfied, then this is a good quality for themselves, (relative quality/customer interest).

However as the customers services will be better when you keep providing services in absolute, with the best services namely; (1) the service is timely, accurate service (2), (3) the giver a polite and friendly service, (4) a full-service facility, (5) services easier and cheaper, service (6)vary, (7) the availability of personal services, (8) service comfortable and conducive, 9) quality of service may be accountable, Margono, (sudadio, 2015:23).

The success of the organization is largely determined by the applied management model, whereas the success of management largely determined by its leader, therefore, when you want the best quality, then the apply quality management. On the basis of this, to know the contribution of management, in particular the integrated services quality management (MMJT) in support of educational success, I tried to do a study of inductive and deductive, with the focus of study namely; The contribution of integrated Service quality management in improving the quality of the results. .The national exam In primary and secondary education in the province of Banten, Java, this study I did in the year 2011, the topic of this study I of view relevant to my area of expertise as a professor in the field of Administrative Sciences in education, as a result of this study is ; 1) 0.216 MMJT contribute

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to a. .in improving the quality of the results of national examination in primary school (elementary school), 2) 0.242, MMJT contribute in improving the quality of the results of national examination in junior high school (MIDDLE SCHOOL) and, 3) 0.202. .MMJT contribute in improving the quality of the results of national examination in the secondary school (HIGH SCHOOL).

Based on the results of this study I believe, that the Quality of the Integrated Services model Manajemen (MMJT) "if implemented well and truly believed able to provide advantages for the institution, that can improve the quality and productivity

Costs and causes of low Quality

High tuition fees would not necessarily produce a good quality, however to get a good quality cost required. .As for the definition of quality is cost; "costs that occur or may occur due to poor quality, Tjipto, Pandi, 2003, (Sudadio, 2015:24).

The cost of a high quality, can occur as a result of Quality Loss Function (QLF), such as: the presence of repair costs and jobs, as well as the delay in the completion of the service, when it is illustrated in the activities of learning at the University or institution, then more and more ..Improving the value and the longer the completion of the study, the higher the quality costs needed, on the contrary, the faster and more accurate, the completion of the study, the lower the quality costs required. this quality cost will be higher if the various causes of low quality are not ..eliminated like; 1) lack of management attention, 2) indifference to aspirations / customer complaints, 3) nonstandard services, 4) prolonged service, 5) service too slow ..., and origin, 6) lack of employee welfare, and 7) ignoring the nature of customers.

Education policy

For this reason, relevant policies are needed in blanking and siding and relevant for the implementation of education in the 21st century with the 4.0 industrial revolution. There should be various factors affecting the occurrence of this Quality Loss Function (QLF) which should have been eliminated, or at least corrected and refined according to demands in order to meet and satisfy customers' needs, if not and even allowed to go bankrupt, it is believed that ultimately the education world in this nation will be increasingly left behind, even quantitatively, especially from the qualitative aspects .more objective and applied.

21st century competencies to face the revolution of 4.0

The 21st century is digital ... free limit, free range, free of delays, non deskriminasi. .The 21st century is the century in gemgaman, because each student is able to obtain information in a broad scope from a variety of sources through cyber space or virtual space by using the call gemgam in his hand or use a computer that's integrated with the internet network. This is where the role of the teacher is to create its own curriculum which can make students learn actively, using various models of learning that suits the development of technology, especially information technology by utilizing again Communication-related activities pembelajaran in the form of e-learning. According to Rosenberg (2001), e-learning is the use of internet technologies in the delivery of learning in a broad range based on three criteria, namely: (1) e-learning; is the network with the ability to update, save, distributes, and share learning materials ..In line with the development of the ICT.

The role of sekolah in facing the 21st century, 1) formulate policy school for new skills, develop new directions 2) curriculum, 3) implementing new learning models and relevant, 4) form a partnership school present local, regional, national, and global. The role of the school will be effective if accompanied by and follow the teacher's performance reflects the teacher teaching the 21st century, according to Ragwan Alaydrus, that in carrying out the activities of 21st century learning, teacher mencerminkan things namely; 1) Life long learning for life, a learner, 2) creative ..and innovative, creative students who will be born from the creative and innovative teachers, 3) apply learning blended learning i.e. combines many different tardsionla approach with the use of digital technology and online media that are relevant, 4) that is, reflective teachers are sensitive to a variety of ..pembeajaran model applied to experience a match or mismatch, so the lack of penigkatan the quality of the learning outcomes can be monitored as well, 5) collaborative teacher may co-operate with the students and with other teachers who are healthy, warm and mutual respect, and bekolaborasi with people.old, 6) apply a student centered, 7) apply the approach derefreshnsi; teachers design classes in accordance with the student's learning style, so will the creation of susana class nman and secure (kondusiv).

With the active role of schools and teachers in understanding the patterns and models, as well as 21st century learning in order to prepare human resources who have the ability to Excel in the face of a range of developments and progress of the industrial revolution, then 4.0 each graduate is required to have a. .various competencies that are reliable, adaptive and can be used as a handle in dealing with various complex and complex challenges that sometimes fluctuate so quickly and unpredictably, even tend and beyond the ability of an average human being, this condition is impossible to be followed and addressed in ways that are routine, and in ordinary ways, for this we need individuals who have high ability, willingness and dedication, which is

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derived from the learning outcomes, for this and the 21st century competencies that should be possessed by every student or student, is namely ; critical thinking, 2) creative, 3) communicative and, 4) collaborative.

The 21st Century, divided into three types of generations namely; 1) group. .Generation X for groups born in 1970 and early 1980, 2) Generation Y for birth groups in the 1980s, 3) Generation Z for groups born in the 1990s until now, this generation is often referred to as the millennial generation.

The generation Y generation is more sophisticated to adapt to computers and the internet. Today's productive age is for young generation Y executives, while generation Z is the age of junior high school students today. .We can see some of them are so used to and master the digital world, internet, multimedia. This era of the school should be able to accommodate the needs and skills of children.

The process of 21st century teaching and learning

According to Ian J Mc Coog, some past era, when we went to school, we know that ... as reading, riting (writing) and rithmetic (arithmetic), versus in the 21st century now that ... better known as rigor, relevance and real world skills. .Characteristics of the 21st century according to Kemendikbud is the availability of information anywhere and anytime (information}, the implementation of the use of computing machines, capable of reaching all the work routine (Automation) and can be done from anywhere and everywhere (communications). .It was found that in the past 20 years has happened educational development shift towards ICT as one of the 21st century management education strategy which includes institutional governance and human resources (Soderstrom, From , Lovqvist, & Tornquist, ..2011) 1, whereas a feature of the 21st century according to Hernawan (Hidayat and Patras) 2 is the increasing interactions between citizens of the world either directly or indirectly, more information is available and can be obtained, wider horizons intellectually, the emergence of the current openness and democracation in both the political and the economic, the cultural distance this long between the older generation and the younger generation, the increasing awareness of the necessity of the world balance is maintained, the growing awareness of economic interdependence, and mengaburnya limits the sovereignty of certain cultures due to No obstruction of information.

This is century requires the transformation of education thoroughly so awakened teacher quality capable of advancing knowledge, training, the student equity and student achievement (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Azam & Kingdon, 2014), and according to Patrick Slattery in his book entitled Curriculum .. Development In The Postmodern i.e. education based on some concept of IE; 1) education shall be directed to social change, community empowerment, the liberation of the mind, body and spirit, 2) education shall be based on the seven main thing on refers to the concept of ..developed by Thich Nhat Hanh, i.e. not tied to theory, ideology, and religion; don't think narrow that knowledge possessed is the most true; do not impose the will on others either by power, threats, propaganda or an educator; care about the ..Sesame; do not keep the hatred and rage; don't lose your identity; do not work in places that destroy human beings and nature, 3) the context of learning, the development of kurikulum research and applied as a chance to connect students with the universe (kontektual), 4) Make teachers feel prosperous activities in learning

Education which implements the vision of the 21th century, 21th century readiness is in readiness to welcome the 21st century. .UNESCO has made four (4) education pillars to welcome the 21st century, namely: a) Learning to how (learning to learn), b) Learning to do (learning to do), c) Learning to be (learn to actualize ourselves as individual self-contained personality, d) Learning to live ..together (learn to live together).Education that builds competence in the 21st Century Learning partnership is a 21st century learning framework that requires students to have the skills, knowledge and abilities in the field of technology, media and information, learning skills, innovation, life skills and competence21st Century Learning partnership refers to Hermawan (2006) 21st century education format, namely: 1) Cyber (e-learning) where learning is done by optimizing use, 2) Open and distance learning where 21st century learning can be done with a model .distance learning, is not limited and is carried out by utilizing the help of information and communication technology, 3) Quantum Learning, namely applying learning methods that are adapted to the way of work, 4) Cooperative Learning, namely learning that uses groups as an effort ..fostering collaboration between, 5) Society of Technology Science, which is an interdisciplinary concept that is applied to integrate problems in science, technology and society, 6) accelerated learning, namely developing the ability to absorb and understand information .fast so that it can improve learning skills more effectively.

RESEARCH METHODS

We Research as for used in this research is qualitative research we compress and kunatitatif, while to get the data in this study, researchers acted as the human instrument and use guidelines the collection of data in the form of the now, guidelines ..observation and interview guidelines are derived from the respective data sources five people five teachers at elementary

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schools, five high schools and five orangbguru in lima senior high school, taken in random in six cities and counties diprovinsi Banten in the year 2017. To process and analyze the data, qualitative analysis using the technique of penelitia deskriptif with the stage; 1) reduction, 2) verification and 3), while for triangulation mengola and analyze the data quantitatively, the author uses descriptive statistical with the simple formula that is mean.

RESEARCH OF RESULTS

Of observation and interviews as well as supported by the results of analsisi data by using descriptive statistics, then brings about that; Policy Contributions in improving the quality of Education of the 21st century the Era of the industrial revolution 4.0. in Banten Province., it can be stated, namely average educational management contribution in donating quality results of the study in the elementary school, middle school ..first and secondary school; berkotribusi is quite good. Following visualization education management contribution in improving the quality of education services are visualized with the value of the results of the study exams elementary school, first middle school, and upper secondary school are as seen on the following image.

Figure 2, Graph Contributions policy and management education

When in analysis management contribution figures as tervisualisasi in where the management is one of the variables from the variable quality of education sebagaimana the eighth set forth in the regulation/policy specifically informing the minimum quality in .education, as set forth in a Government Regulation No 19 of the year 2005, which was revised in the Government Regulation No. 32 year 2013 are: 1) the standard of competence of graduates, 2) standards of contents, 3) standard process, standard 4) educators, 5) saranaprasarana, stnadar 6 statndar management), 7) standards.financing and, 8) standard assessment of education, which is the eighth standard is already supposed to have the same stnadar throughout wiyah schools in the unitary State of Republic of Indonesia, melalui standardization in continuity and continuous improvement. Standardization system is carried out well and objectively, it is expected that there will be no quality divisions between one school and another, between rural schools and schools in urban areas.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that; Contribution of Education Policy and Management Integrated in Improving the Quality of 21st Century Education Services Industrial Revolution Era 4.0. in Banten Province, can be stated as contributing quite well.

Hopefully in the next research or other researchers can develop this research on other variables this research can be declared quite reliable with research conducted in 2011 with relatively problems and data sources, where the results are only there is a difference in decline or an average increase of five percent.

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